

		Standard Operating Procedure SOP-AVITHRAPID-ANTIVIRAL ACTIVITY on HEV by qPCR_VIRUCIDAL CMP
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Version:	1	
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	Created by	Controlled by	Approved by
Name	Anne Bull-Maurer	Julien Marlet	Fabrizio Mammano
Email	anne.bull@univ-tours.fr	julien.marlet@univ-tours.fr	fabrizio.mammano@univ-tours.fr
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1. Goal and Area of Application

When evaluating the antiviral effect of a compound, assessing cellular toxicity in the target cell line is an essential prerequisite (see SOP ‘AVITHRAPID - Standard Operating Procedure - Cytotoxicity evaluation – virucidal compounds’ at <https://zenodo.org/records/20486126>). The highest dose allowing > 90 % cell viability is the first tested dose in antiviral assay. Quantifying viruses in the supernatants of infected cell cultures enables the evaluation of the antiviral efficacy of compounds. PLC3 differentiated cells are used for HEV infection studies.

2. Definitions and Abbreviations

CMPs	Compounds
HEV	Hepatitis E Virus
qPCR	quantitative Polymerase Chain Reaction
RT-PCR	Retrotranscription followed by Polymerase Chain Reaction

3. Method

3.1 General

This SOP describes the evaluation of antiviral efficacy of virucidal compounds by quantitative Polymerase Chain Reaction on the supernatant of HEV infected PLC3 differentiated cells. Virucidal compounds act directly on the virus and are pre-incubated with viruses before cell infection. This technique implies cell infection with a complete virus and therefore requires a BSL-3 facility.

PLC3 cells are a subclone of PLC/PRF/5 hepatoma cell line, commonly used for HEV replication studies. Differentiation of these cells leads to polarisation that better reproduces the hepatocyte architecture *in vivo*, further increasing the susceptibility of these cells to HEV infection and promoting viral replication. PLC3 cells differentiation is achieved following the dedicated SOP ‘AVITHRAPID - Standard Operating Procedure - PLC3 cells differentiation before HEV infection’ (<https://zenodo.org/records/20485859>)

The antiviral efficacy of a compound is measured by incubating a constant dose of virus with dilutions of the compound. Supernatant from HEV infected PLC3 cells is harvested 4, 6 and 8 days after infection. After viral RNA extraction, a one-step quantitative RT-PCR (Taqman technology) is performed to determine the % of inhibition by the relative reduction of target RNA in treated sample as compared to untreated infected control.

Note : For Light-sensitive compounds, tests have to be performed in dark condition

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3.2 Information for consommables / chemicals /equipment

Product name	Supplier	Ordering n°
DMEM High Glucose	Gibco	61965059
Fetal Bovine Serum	e.g. Gibco	e.g. 10270-106
Penicillin/Streptomycin	Gibco	15140
DMSO	Sigma	472301
Ribavirine	Clinisciences	HY-B0434
Sterile 96 well culture plate, flat bottom (polystyrene)	e.g. Dutscher	e.g. 353072
PLC3 cells (a clone of PLC/PRF/5 cells)	Gift from CIIL, Center for Infection & Immunity of Lille, France	
HEV viral stock	In house - supernatant of infected PLC3	
Quick Extract RNA	Euromedex	QER090150
Luna® Universal Probe One-Step RT-qPCR Kit	NEB	E3006X
Investigational compounds		

Equipment		
Thermocycler	Roche	Light cycler 480

3.3 Procedure

PLC3 differentiated cells are obtained by following the dedicated SOP: AVITHRAPID - Standard Operating Procedure - PLC3 cells differentiation before HEV infection (<https://zenodo.org/records/20485859>)

3.3.1 Cell seeding + control drug treatment (DAY 0)

PLC3 differentiated cells (22,000 cells/well) are seeded in DMEM 10% FCS P/S in flat-bottom 96-well plates

Plates are then incubated at 37°C in a humidified atmosphere with 5% CO₂ for 16h to allow proper adhesion and stabilization

3.3.2 Virus + compound pre-incubation (DAY 1)

Note: For compounds sensitive to light, tests have to be performed IN DARK CONDITION

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- First the initial stock solutions of compounds are diluted to the double of the highest non-toxic concentration in the appropriate medium (including DMSO if needed for compound solubility) to account for the further 2-fold dilution due to mixing with the virus.
- Then serial dilutions with a 2-fold dilution ratio are carried out in the appropriate medium.
- A viral solution at $1,6 \cdot 10^8$ IU/mL is mixed 1:1 (50 μ L virus + 50 μ L CMP) with the compounds' dilutions to obtain the desired range of concentrations.
- A 1:1 mix of DMEM 0% FCS and the CMPs dilutions will be used as non-infected, treated control.
- The mixes are incubated 1h under agitation at 37°C in a humidified atmosphere with 5% CO₂

3.3.3 Cells infection (DAY 1)

- PLC3 cells are treated with the dilutions of viruses + CMP (100 μ L per well)
- Positive control wells (n = 6) consisted of PLC3 cells infected with the corresponding viral dilutions in the absence of any drug treatment.
- Negative control wells contained non-infected PLC3 cells.
- The plates were incubated overnight at 37°C in a humidified atmosphere with 5% CO₂

3.3.4 Medium renewal and Ribavirin treatment (DAY 2)

- Cells are washed 3-times with PBS1X and 200 μ L of DMEM 2% FCS was added per well
- Half of positive controls (3 wells) are treated with Ribavirin 50 μ M. The second half of positive controls and the negative control wells are not treated with drugs.

3.3.5 Medium renewal and supernatant harvesting (DAY 4, DAY 6 and DAY 8)

Medium is renewed at days 4, 6 and 8 (collect 10 μ L medium each time)

Plates are incubated at 37°C in a humidified atmosphere with 5% CO₂ throughout the duration of the test

3.3.6 Viral RNA extraction and quantitative RT-PCR analysis (Taqman technology)

RNA extraction

For HEV RNA preparation, 10 μ L of cell culture supernatant is combined with 10 μ L of QuickExtract™ reagent in a 96-well plate to achieve rapid viral lysis. The mixture is incubated

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at 65 °C for 6 min to promote cell and virion disruption, followed by heating at 98 °C for 2 min to inactivate enzymes and potential nucleases. Samples are then cooled at 4 °C for 5 min. An optional DNase treatment can be performed according to the manufacturers' instructions. To minimize the presence of PCR inhibitors associated with the crude lysate, 80 µL of nuclease-free PCR water is added, resulting in a 1:5 dilution. A total of 5 µL of the diluted lysate is subsequently used as input for RT-qPCR. All samples are processed and analyzed on the same day to avoid RNA degradation and repeated freeze–thaw cycles.

Quantitative RT-PCR analysis

Primers and Probe

ORF3s_qPCR	GGTGGTTTCTGGGGTGAC
ORF3as_qPCR	AGGGGTTGGTTGGATGAA
HEVORF3_p	FAM–TGATTCTCAGCCCTTCGC–BHQ1 200 nmol

Reaction mixes and Light cycler LC480 settings

Master mix:

Luna Universal Probe One-Step Reaction Mix:	10.0 µL
RT Enzyme Mix (20X):	1.0 µL
Forward primer (10 µM):	1 µL
Reverse primer (10 µM):	1 µL
Probe (10 µM):	0.5 µL
RNA template:	5 µL
complete with water up to 20 µL	

Cycling profile:

Reverse Transcription:	55°C x 15 minutes (1 cycle)
Initial Denaturation:	95°C 1 minute (1 cycle)
Amplification (45 cycles):	95°C 20 seconds (Denaturation) 60°C x 1 min (Extension + signal acquisition)
Cooling:	40°C 30 seconds

3.3.7 Data analysis and interpretation

Samples HEV viral loads are calculated using QS3 calibrant from RealStar HEV RT-PCR Kit 2.0 (cod.272023, Altona) a standard for quantification corresponding to 1.0E+05 IU/mL.

All experiments are conducted with three technical replicates (three wells) per condition on each plate and are independently repeated on three separate experimental days. For data analysis, the mean value of the three technical replicates from each independent experiment is

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calculated, yielding three independent mean data points per condition. These values are used to perform statistical analyses and IC₅₀ calculations using GraphPad Prism. Viral replication in the positive control condition (no treatment) is set to 100% and used for normalization.

Statistical analyses and IC₅₀ calculations on GraphPad Prism.

On Graphpad Prism, the mean and SEM % of viral replication for each tested doses are plotted. The IC₅₀ is calculated using XY Analysis -> non linear regression (curve fit) [Inhibitor] vs. response (three parameters). The 95% Confidence Interval can also be shown as in the examples here below.

4. Further applicable documents

- AVITHRAPID - Standard Operating Procedure - PLC3 cells differentiation before HEV infection (<https://zenodo.org/records/20485859>)